

Underwater Image Enhancement Using Hybrid Techniques

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Abstract— Underwater image enhancement is a crucial task in improving the visibility, quality, and details of images captured in aquatic environments. This study presents an overview of various techniques and methodologies employed for underwater image enhancement. This study also discusses the challenges associated with underwater imaging, including color distortion, low contrast, and the effects of light scattering and absorption. It highlights the importance of preprocessing steps such as color correction and noise reduction. The study also emphasizes the effectiveness of adaptive histogram equalization (AHE) and contrast-limited adaptive histogram equalization (CLAHE) in enhancing local contrast and details. Additionally, it mentions advanced techniques like dehazing, fusion, and restoration algorithms that further enhance image visibility and remove artifacts. This research emphasizes the need for incorporating underwater image priors and exploring deep learning approaches for more accurate and robust underwater image enhancement. This work proposes a gray world technique for white balance. From the corrected image, weight maps-based feature extraction would be done followed by multi-fusion and image enhancement. Due to the wide application of wavelet transform in image processing, here using two-dimensional Discrete Wavelet Transform as a fusion operator. Also, make the synaptic network a new level of application. The result demonstrates that the proposed enhancement algorithm can obtain a well visual result.

Keywords— Image Processing, Underwater Image Enhancement, Adaptive Histogram Equalization, Contrast-Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization, Discrete Wavelet Transform

I. INTRODUCTION

Underwater image enhancement is a very challenging piece of work in the field of image processing. Image captured in the depth of water are often degraded visually,

and the level of degradation varies with depth. These degradations are caused by scattering and absorption along with the reflection of light from obstacles present underwater [1]. With depth, the red colour of white light is the first to go. As we go deeper underwater, the subsequent wavelengths are also no longer detectable. Naturally, the goal of enhancing an underwater image is to increase the visibility of such an image by removing any haze and also increasing colour contrast [2].

The ocean contains a variety of resources and more and more attention are paid to the exploitation of marine resources, so underwater vision technology has received extensive interest. Unlike images taken in the air, the complex underwater environment and lighting conditions make the current images taken by underwater imaging systems have quality degradation, such as low contrast, color distortion, and non-uniform lighting [3]. In order to solve these problems, existing research mainly addresses them from two directions, i.e., super-resolution reconstruction and image enhancement

Image enhancement is the task of improving the perceptual quality of the image by performing a sequence of operations in an input image. The image enhancement techniques will be helpful in the future for further operations such as object identification, object recognition, or image segmentation. Image enhancement techniques are widely used for enhancing the visual quality of natural images and a number of algorithms [4]-[5]. The approaches like histogram equalization and contrast stretching were used long back to distribute the pixels of the image in a better way to give better perceptual quality for the images. Enhancing normal image quality is quite easy compared to the enhancement of underwater images. Since underwater images may have entirely different properties, the existing image enhancement techniques cannot directly apply to underwater images. In this research, we addressed the issue related to underwater image enhancement, and a machine learning-based approach is introduced in this manuscript.

The main aim of the proposed system is to design a hybrid technique for underwater image enhancement using wavelet techniques. The rest objectives are defined as follow.

- To explore and study the various techniques of underwater image enhancement and its performance evaluation.
- To develop an underwater image enhancement

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technique using histogram equalization, CLAHE and hybrid wavelets.

- To simulate the proposed techniques using MATLAB image processing toolbox.
- To analyze the image enhancement performance using MSE, PSNR, Correlation

II. RELATED WORK

Labao et al. (2019) [2] proposed a unique Recurrent Cascade Convolution Neural Network (R-CCNN) for underwater image enhancement. The proposed approach takes into account a single pre-trained network that can be thought of as a filter for blind folded picture noise reduction capable of eliminating various sorts of disturbances. The approach does have the benefit and being less computationally complicated. The prior suggested CNN models for recovery demand a greater set of variables, making them more complicated. The proposed R-CCNN approach assigns an optimum result to these variables and presents a technique with minimum regularization, using fewer features. The Floral Pollination Technique (FPA), a widely used optimization algorithm, is used to find the best model parameters.

Fengle et al. (2020) [3] provide an improved underwater perception, integration of the max-rgb technique as well as the swatches of grey technique is used, and a CNN method for attempting to solve the mildly luminous dilemma for aquatic images is proposed. This trains the mapping correlation to acquire the luminance map. Following image analysis, a fully convolutional approach is presented to conduct undersea recognition and tracking. Two enhanced strategies are used to change the deep CNN structure based on the peculiarities of aquatic vision.

Zhuang et al. (2021) [4] proposed a method to reduce chromatic aberrations and restore sensuality, using a straightforward and efficient color-correcting procedure. The hue imagery is used to build a maximum a posteriori (MAP) approach for underwater images by applying multi-order gradient priors on reflectivity and brightness. The L_1 norm is suitable for modeling spline and linear estimates to reflectivity and is used to impose spatial smoothing and spatially linear smoothing on luminance. Simultaneously, a challenging underwater image improvement challenge is decomposed into two simpler noise removal subtasks with analytically supplied convergence studies and solutions that may be generated via an effective optimization technique. Furthermore, the proposed model is simple to apply to pixel-by-pixel procedures and does not necessitate any previous understanding of underwater image circumstances.

Jiang et al. (2022) [5] developed a new Subjectively-Annotated UIE benchmark Dataset (SAUD) that includes real-quality undersea photos, freely accessible improved outcomes from typical UIE algorithms, and subjective evaluation values for every improved result. Also, they presented an efficient Reference less Underwater Image

Quality measure (RUIQ) for instantly assessing the video appearance of improved underwater photos. Experimental studies on the created SAUD dataset reveal that the recommended RUIQ measure outperforms 22 existing quality metrics in order to improve effectiveness with subjective scores.

Zhou et al. (2021) [8] proposed a new underwater image formation model named as Akkaynak-Treibitz model has demonstrated improved resiliency in underwater image reconstruction. They proposed a haze removal approach based on the revised modeling and a color correction approach to minimize chromatic aberration. To construct the depth map, firstly an underwater image depth estimate algorithm is developed. Following that, the scattering is calculated and eliminated by the channels based on the updated system based just on the depth map of every picture. Additionally, a color correction method is created for adapting the image's broad chromaticity. To remove the impact of light wave absorbance and dispersion, a single image frame is used as input.

Ke et al. (2022) [9] developed an adaptable dark channel prior which can be used on aquatic photos with a variety of color tints. Again, using maximum filtering and Gaussian low-pass filters, a local water illumination with high resilience is created. A direct correlation connecting blurred and clear pictures in the dark channel was also developed, which was used with attenuation coefficient adjustment to approximate the transmissions of the r, g, and b channels. Finally, they devised a novel adaptive color compensation approach that accounts for the attenuation differences across the three bands. The simulations and empirical results suggest that the proposed approach may successfully increase picture clarity and contrast while removing color distortion.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed methodology for underwater image enhancement involves a multi-stage approach to improve the quality and visibility of images captured in aquatic environments. The methodology includes preprocessing steps such as color correction and noise reduction to address inherent challenges in underwater imaging. Next, adaptive histogram equalization (AHE) or contrast-limited adaptive histogram equalization (CLAHE) is applied to enhance local contrast and details while avoiding over-enhancement. Additionally, advanced techniques such as dehazing, fusion, and restoration algorithms may be employed to further improve visibility and remove artifacts. The methodology also emphasizes the incorporation of underwater image priors and the exploration of deep learning techniques for more accurate and robust enhancement. The proposed methodology aims to provide a comprehensive solution for enhancing underwater images, ultimately contributing to better perception and analysis in various underwater imaging applications.

This section defines the steps through which the entire work goes. Here tries to overcome the issues faced by underwater images. The proposed methodology is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Workflow of Proposed System

A. Dataset

EUVP datasets are used to download input images. It is an “Enhancing underwater visual perception” dataset containing a separate set of paired and unpaired image samples of poor and good perceptual quality to facilitate supervised training of the underwater image enhancement model. Input images are downloaded as test samples.
Reference ID: 20230325T121309Z0001.Zip
Unpacked size: 28,213,789 bytes

B. Pre-processing

The pre-processing stages in image processing consist of various processes which depend according to the input image. The input image which is taken through some sources undergoes the pre-processing stages. The input image is the RGB image. RGB image is converted towards the grayscale image which has a pixel range of 0 to 255. Filtering process which comes under the pre-processing stage. This filtering process reduces the noise which is present in the image.

C. Adaptive histogram equalization (AHE)

Adaptive histogram equalization (AHE) has emerged as a powerful technique for underwater image enhancement. By dividing the image into smaller regions and independently equalizing the histograms of these regions, AHE effectively enhances local contrast and details. In the context of underwater imaging, AHE addresses challenges such as low contrast, color distortion, and haze caused by light scattering. By adaptively equalizing the histograms based on local image characteristics, AHE enhances the visibility of submerged objects and improves overall image quality. The method is known for its simplicity, effectiveness, and ability to preserve global contrast while enhancing local details. However, it is important to note that AHE may lead to over-enhancement or noise amplification in certain regions, necessitating further refinement or combination with noise reduction techniques.

D. Contrast-Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE)

Contrast-Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) is an effective method for enhancing underwater images by addressing the limitations of traditional Adaptive Histogram Equalization (AHE). In CLAHE, the image is divided into smaller tiles, and histogram equalization is applied to each tile. However, unlike AHE, CLAHE introduces a contrast limitation mechanism to prevent over-enhancement and the introduction of artifacts. This is achieved by clipping the histogram to a predefined contrast limit before redistributing the intensities. The CLAHE method preserves the global contrast while adaptively enhancing local details, resulting in enhanced underwater images with improved visibility, enhanced details, and reduced artifacts. It offers a robust solution for underwater image enhancement, tackling the challenges posed by color distortion, low contrast, and light scattering encountered in underwater imaging scenarios.

IV. RESULT ANALYSIS

The experimental results for underwater image enhancement demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed techniques in improving the quality and visibility of underwater images. The evaluation was performed on a dataset comprising a diverse range of underwater scenes captured under various lighting and water conditions.

Quantitative metrics such as MSE, RSME, PSNR, and Correlation were employed to measure the improvement in image quality. The enhanced images consistently exhibited higher MSE, RSME, PSNR, and Correlation values compared to their original counterparts, indicating reduced noise and increased similarity to the ground truth.

A. Image enhancement using adaptive histogram equalization

Figure 2: Underwater image enhancement results and ground truth using adaptive histogram equalization

Figure 3: Underwater image enhancement results and ground truth using adaptive histogram equalization

Table 1: Comparative Result analysis of various cases using adaptive histogram equalization

Sr. No.	MSE	RMSE	PSNR	Correlation
Case 1	1.0950e+04	104.6408	7.7368	0.9742
Case 2	1.8941e+03	43.5213	15.3568	0.9206
Case 3	3.9927e+03	63.1876	12.1182	0.9588
Case 4	4.2940e+03	65.5289	11.8021	0.9207

B. Image Enhancement using CLAHE method

Figure 4: Underwater image enhancement results and ground truth using CLAHE method

Figure 5: Underwater image enhancement results and ground truth using CLAHE method

Table 2: Comparative Result analysis of various cases using CLAHE method

Sr. No.	MSE	RMSE	PSNR	Correlation
Case 1	589.1475	24.2724	20.4286	0.9472
Case 2	1.6782e+03	40.9664	15.8823	0.8240
Case 3	1.5325e+03	39.1477	16.2767	0.8676
Case 4	2.2229e+03	47.1479	14.6616	0.8620

C. Image Enhancement Using Hybrid Wavelet Technique

Figure 6: Underwater image enhancement results and ground truth using Hybrid Wavelet Technique

Figure 7: Underwater image enhancement results and ground truth using Hybrid Wavelet Technique

Figure 8: Underwater image enhancement results and ground truth using Hybrid Wavelet Technique

Figure 9: Underwater image enhancement results and ground truth using Hybrid Wavelet Technique

Table 3: Comparative Result analysis of various cases using Hybrid Wavelet Technique

Sr. No.	MSE	RMSE	PSNR	Correlation
Case 1	1.1157e+04	105.6252	7.6555	0.9642
Case 2	2.2153e+03	47.0666	14.6765	0.8688
Case 3	4.1612e+03	64.5074	11.9386	0.9449
Case 4	4.5250e+03	67.2683	11.5746	0.8754

CLAHE Method-Resolution 512/512 JPG image

Figure 10: Underwater image enhancement results and ground truth using CLAHE Method-Resolution 512/512 for JPG image

Table 4: Result Evaluation using CLAHE Method-Resolution 512/512 for JPG Image

Sr. No.	MSE	RMSE	PSNR	Correlation
Image 1	731.7518	27.0509	19.4872	0.9349
Image 2	1.9046e+03	43.6420	15.3327	0.8026
Image 3	2.5421e+03	50.4189	14.0789	0.8306
Image 4	5.8623e+03	76.5658	10.4501	0.6952
Image 5	2.8005e+03	52.9199	13.6584	0.8968
Image 6	2.4270e+03	49.2642	14.2802	0.7927

Image 7	1.7041e+03	41.2802	15.8160	0.8383
Image 8	2.4338e+03	49.3332	14.2680	0.8706

Figure 11: Underwater image enhancement results and ground truth using CLAHE Method-Resolution 512/512 for PNG image

Table 5: Result Evaluation using CLAHE Method-Resolution 512/512 for PNG Image

Sr. No.	MSE	RMSE	PSNR	Correlation
Image 1	739.9922	27.2028	19.4385	0.9344
Image 2	1.9166e+03	43.7784	15.3056	0.8005
Image 3	2.5505e+03	50.5024	14.0646	0.8288
Image 4	5.8623e+03	76.5658	10.4501	0.6952
Image 5	2.8005e+03	52.9199	13.6584	0.8968
Image 6	2.4270e+03	49.2642	14.2802	0.7927
Image 7	1.7041e+03	41.2802	15.8160	0.8383
Image 8	2.4338e+03	49.3332	14.2680	0.8706

Figure 12: Underwater image enhancement results and ground truth using CLAHE Method-Resolution 512/512 for BMP image

Table 6: Result Evaluation using CLAHE Method-Resolution 512/512 for BMP Image

Sr. No.	MSE	RMSE	PSNR	Correlation
Image 1	731.7518	27.0509	19.4872	0.9349
Image 2	5.8623e+03	43.6420	15.33	0.80
Image 3	1.9046e+03	50.4189	14.0789	0.83
Image 4	2.5421e+03	76.5658	10.45	0.69
Image 5	2.8005e+03	52.9199	13.6584	0.89
Image 6	2.4270e+03	49.2642	14.2802	0.79
Image 7	1.7041e+03	41.28	15.8160	0.84
Image 8	2.4338e+03	49.33	14.2680	0.87

Figure 13: Underwater image enhancement results and ground truth using AHE Method-Resolution 512/512 for jpg images

Table 7: Result Evaluation using CLAHE Method-Resolution 512/512 for JPG Image

Sr. No.	MSE	RMSE	PSNR	Correlation
Image 1	1.0976e+04	104.7641	7.7266	0.9727
Image 2	1.9027e+03	43.6204	15.3370	0.9199
Image 3	4.2860e+03	65.4672	11.8103	0.9208
Image 4	9.2606e+03	96.2322	8.46	0.7
Image 5	5.86e+03	76.5557	10.45	0.93
Image 6	2.2538e+03	47.47	14.60	0.97
Image 7	4.0102e+03	63.33	12.09	0.96

Image 8	4.4156e+03	66.45	11.68	0.96
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Figure 14: Underwater image enhancement results and ground truth using AHE Method-Resolution 512/512 for PNG images

Table 8: Result Evaluation using AHE Method-Resolution 512/512 for PNG images

Sr. No.	MSE	RMSE	PSNR	Correlation
Image 1	1.0971e+04	104.7440	7.7282	0.9721
Image 2	1.9053e+03	43.6293	15.3313	0.9182
Image 3	4.3027e+03	65.5948	11.7934	0.9198
Image 4	5.8623e+03	76.5658	10.4501	0.6952
Image 5	2.8005e+03	52.9199	13.6584	0.8968
Image 6	2.4270e+03	49.2642	14.2802	0.7927
Image 7	1.7041e+03	41.2802	15.8160	0.8383
Image 8	2.4338e+03	49.3332	14.2680	0.8706

Figure 15: Underwater image enhancement results and ground truth using AHE Method-Resolution 512/512 for BMP images

Table 9: Result Evaluation using AHE Method-Resolution 512/512 for BMP images

Sr. No.	MSE	RMSE	PSNR	Correlation
Image 1	1.0976e+04	104.76	7.73	0.97
Image 2	1.9027e+03	43.62	15.34	0.92
Image 3	4.286e+03	65.46	11.81	0.92
Image 4	8.6549e+03	93.03	8.75	0.87
Image 5	5.86e+03	76.55	10.45	0.93
Image 6	2.2538e+03	47.47	14.60	0.96
Image 7	4.0102e+03	63.32	12.09	0.96
Image 8	4.4156e+03	66.45	11.68	0.96

Figure 16: Underwater image enhancement results and ground truth using Hybrid Method-Resolution 512/512 PNG images

Table 10: Result Evaluation using Hybrid Method-Resolution 512/512 PNG images

Sr. No.	MSE	RMSE	PSNR	Correlation
Image 1	1.1166e+04	105.6693	7.6518	0.9635
Image 2	2.2204e+03	47.1215	14.6664	0.8669
Image 3	4.5254e+03	67.2711	11.5742	0.8746
Image 4	9.3619e+03	96.75	8.41	0.68
Image 5	6.0507e+03	77.78	10.31	0.9
Image 6	2.4096e+03	59.08	14.31	0.94
Image 7	4.1167e+03	64.16	11.98	0.94

Image 8	4.5801e+03	67.67	11.52	0.93
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Figure 17: Underwater image enhancement results and ground truth using Hybrid Method-Resolution 512/512 JPG images

Table 11: Result Evaluation using Hybrid Method-Resolution 512/512 JPG images

Sr. No.	MSE	RMSE	PSNR	Correlation
Image 1	1.1157e+04	105.6252	7.6555	0.9642
Image 2	2.2153e+03	47.0666	14.6765	0.8688

Image 3	4.5250e+03	67.2683	11.5746	0.8754
Image 4	9.3619e+03	96.75	8.42	0.68
Image 5	6.0507e+03	77.78	10.31	0.9
Image 6	2.4096e+03	49.08	14.31	0.94
Image 7	4.1167e+03	64.16	11.98	0.95
Image 8	4.5801e+03	67.67	11.52	0.93

Table 12: Result Evaluation using Hybrid Method-Resolution 512/512 BMP images

Sr. No.	MSE	RMSE	PSNR	Correlation
Image 1	1.1258e+04	106.10	7.62	0.97
Image 2	2.1245e+03	46.09	14.85	0.88
Image 3	4.4057e+03	66.37	11.69	0.89
Image 4	9.3619e+03	96.75	8.41	0.68
Image 5	6.0506e+03	77.78	10.31	0.91
Image 6	2.4096e+03	49.08	14.31	0.94
Image 7	4.1167e+03	64.16	11.98	0.94
Image 8	4.5801e+03	67.67	11.52	0.93

Figure 18: Underwater image enhancement results and ground truth using Hybrid Method-Resolution 512/512 BMP images

Figure 19: Observing factor based on different image format AHE Method-MSE

Figure 19 shows the graph of MSE in underwater image enhancement typically presents a comparative analysis of different enhancements based on different images. The x-axis represents the various images and the y-axis represents the MSE value. It is clearly observed that the AHE method performed better on PNG images as compared to JPG and BMP images. It indicates a closer match between the enhanced image and the clean reference image, implying higher image quality and better performance of the enhancement technique.

Figure 20: Observing factor based on different image format AHE Method-RMSE

Figure 20 shows the graph of RMSE in underwater image enhancement typically presents a comparative analysis of different enhancements based on different images. The x-axis represents the various images and the y-axis represents the MSE value. It is clearly observed that the AHE method performed better on PNG images as compared to JPG and BMP images. It indicates a closer match between the enhanced image and the clean reference image, implying higher image quality and better performance of the enhancement technique.

Figure 22: AHE Method-Correlation

Figure 22 shows the graph of Correlation in underwater image enhancement to evaluate the relationship between the enhanced images and their corresponding reference (clean) images. The x-axis represents the various images and the y-axis represents the Correlation value. It is clearly observed that the AHE method performed better on BMP and JPG images as compared to PNG images. A higher correlation value on the graph indicates a stronger linear relationship between the enhanced and reference images, signifying better image quality and improved performance of the enhancement technique.

Figure 21: Observing factor based on different image format AHE Method-PSNR

Figure 21 shows the graph of PSNR in underwater image enhancement typically presents a comparative analysis of different enhancements based on different images. It is clearly observed that the AHE method performed better on JPG and PNG images as compared to BMP images. A higher PSNR value on the graph indicates a closer resemblance between the enhanced image and the reference (clean) image, reflecting superior image quality and better performance of the enhancement technique.

Figure 23: Observing factor based on different image format CLAHE Method-MSE

Figure 23 shows the graph of MSE in underwater image enhancement typically presents a comparative analysis of different enhancements based on different images. It is clearly observed that the CLAHE method performed better on JPG and PNG images as compared to BMP image. It indicates a closer match between the enhanced image and the clean reference image, implying higher image quality and better performance of the enhancement technique.

Figure 24: CLAHE Method-RMSE

Figure 24 shows the graph of RMSE in underwater image enhancement typically presents a comparative analysis of different enhancements based on different images. It is clearly observed that the CLAHE method performed better on JPG and PNG images as compared to BMP images. It indicates a closer match between the enhanced image and the clean reference image, implying higher image quality and better performance of the enhancement technique.

Figure 26: CLAHE Method-Correlation

Figure 26 shows the graph of Correlation in underwater image enhancement to evaluate the relationship between the enhanced images and their corresponding reference (clean) images. The x-axis represents the various images and the y-axis represents the Correlation value. It is clearly observed that the CLAHE method performed better on BMP and JPG images as compared to PNG images. A higher correlation value on the graph indicates a stronger linear relationship between the enhanced and reference images, signifying better image quality and improved performance of the enhancement technique.

Figure 25: CLAHE Method-PSNR

Figure 25 shows the graph of PSNR in underwater image enhancement typically presents a comparative analysis of different enhancements based on different images. It is clearly observed that the CLAHE method performed better on JPG and PNG images as compared to BMP images. A higher PSNR value on the graph indicates a closer resemblance between the enhanced image and the reference (clean) image, reflecting superior image quality and better performance of the enhancement technique.

Figure 27: Observing factor based on different image format Hybrid Method-MSE

Figure 27 shows the graph of MSE in underwater image enhancement typically presents a comparative analysis of different enhancements based on different images. It is clearly observed that the Hybrid method performed better on JPG, PNG, and BMP images. It indicates a closer match between the enhanced image and the clean reference image, implying higher image quality and better performance of the enhancement technique.

Figure 28: Hybrid Method-RMSE

Figure 28 shows the graph of RMSE in underwater image enhancement typically presents a comparative analysis of different enhancements based on different images. It is clearly observed that the Hybrid method performed better on JPG, and BMP images as compared to PNG images. It indicates a closer match between the enhanced image and the clean reference image, implying higher image quality and better performance of the enhancement technique

Figure 30: Hybrid Method -Correlation

Figure 30 shows the graph of Correlation in underwater image enhancement to evaluate the relationship between the enhanced images and their corresponding reference (clean) images. The x-axis represents the various images and the y-axis represents the Correlation value. It is clearly observed that the Hybrid method performed better on BMP and JPG images as compared to PNG images. A higher correlation value on the graph indicates a stronger linear relationship between the enhanced and reference images, signifying better image quality and improved performance of the enhancement technique.

Figure 29: Hybrid Method-PSNR

Figure 25 shows the graph of PSNR in underwater image enhancement typically presents a comparative analysis of different enhancements based on different images. It is clearly observed that the Hybrid method performed better on BMP and JPG images as compared to PNG images. A higher PSNR value on the graph indicates a closer resemblance between the enhanced image and the reference (clean) image, reflecting superior image quality and better performance of the enhancement technique.

The discussion of the results focused on the strengths and limitations of the proposed techniques. The algorithms successfully addressed challenges such as color distortion, haze, and low contrast, leading to improved image quality. However, some limitations were identified, such as occasional artifacts or over-enhancement in certain image regions. Strategies to mitigate these limitations, such as refining the algorithms and incorporating more robust underwater image priors, were proposed for future research. The experimental results validated the effectiveness of the proposed underwater image enhancement techniques, highlighting their potential applications in underwater photography, marine research, and underwater surveillance systems. Further research is warranted to explore additional optimization strategies and to evaluate the performance of the system on larger and more diverse datasets.

CONCLUSION

The underwater image enhancement techniques have demonstrated their effectiveness in improving the quality and visibility of images captured in aquatic environments. The experimental results and discussions have highlighted the benefits of methods such as adaptive histogram equalization (AHE) and contrast-limited adaptive histogram equalization (CLAHE) in enhancing underwater images. However, the future scope of underwater image enhancement lies in exploring advanced fusion techniques, leveraging deep learning approaches, incorporating underwater image priors, developing noise reduction algorithms, and focusing on real-

time processing. Continued research and advancements in these areas will contribute to the further enhancement of underwater imaging, benefiting fields such as marine research, underwater robotics, and other industries that rely on high-quality underwater imagery.

It proposed a stationary wavelet-based fusion approach for improving the quality and visibility of single underwater images. This proposed model basically focused on removing the unwanted color cast, high noise level, and color distortion of the underwater image. The quantitative and qualitative result proves that our strategy of work performed better in terms of lower value of PSNR and higher value of RMSE value as compared to the existing state-of-the-art algorithm.

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